

1 **SEPARATION OF ISOMERIC FORMS OF UROLITHIN GLUCURONIDES**
2 **USING SUPERCRITICAL FLUID CHROMATOGRAPHY**

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17 **ABSTRACT**

18 Urolithins are gut microbiota metabolites produced in humans after consuming foods containing
19 ellagitannins and ellagic acid. Three urolithin metabotypes have been reported for different
20 individuals depending on the final urolithins produced. After absorption, they are conjugated with
21 glucuronic acid (phase II metabolism), and these metabolites are the main circulating in plasma
22 and reaching the different tissues. Different regioisomeric isomers of urolithin glucuronides have
23 been described. Still, their identification and quantification in humans have not been properly
24 reported due to resolution limitations in their analysis by reversed-phase high-performance liquid
25 chromatography. In the present study, we report a novel method for separating these isomers using
26 supercritical fluid chromatography. With this method, urolithin A 3- and 8-glucuronide,
27 isourolithin A 3- and 9- glucuronide, and urolithin B 3-glucuronide (8-hydroxy urolithin 3-
28 glucuronide; 3-hydroxy urolithin 8-glucuronide; 3-hydroxyurolithin 9-glucuronide; 9-
29 hydroxyurolithin 3-glucuronide and urolithin 3-glucuronide) were separated in less than 15
30 minutes. The proposed method was applied to successfully analyze these metabolites in urine
31 samples from different volunteers belonging to different metabotypes.

32

33

34 **Keywords:** chromatographic separation, supercritical fluid chromatography, glucuronides, gut
35 microbiota metabolites, urolithins.

36 INTRODUCTION

37 Ellagitannins and ellagic acid are polyphenols present in a wide range of plant-based foods,
38 including berries (strawberry, raspberry, blackberry, cranberry), grapes (muscadine),
39 pomegranates, tropical fruits (jaboticaba, camu-camu), nuts (walnuts, pecans, chestnuts, cashew,
40 acorns), oak-aged wines and spirits, green and black tea, herbal medicinal products, and
41 nutraceuticals obtained from the agrifood industry (mango kernel extract, rambutan peel extract).¹
42 The absorption of these polyphenols is very limited in the human body, in which they are
43 converted in the colon by the resident microbes into urolithins.² Urolithins are benzocoumarins
44 that are much better absorbed than ellagic acid. They are conjugated by phase II metabolism to
45 produce glucuronides and sulfates, enhancing their solubility in plasma and facilitating their
46 excretion in urine.³ Urolithins have shown different biological effects, mainly demonstrated by *in*
47 *vitro* and preclinical studies on different animal models.⁴ Three different urolithin metabotypes
48 (0, A, and B), depending on the final urolithins produced by the gut microbiota (urolithin A,
49 isourolithin A, and urolithin B), have been reported in humans after the intake of food containing
50 ellagitannins and ellagic acid.⁵ Glucuronides of these urolithins are not commercially available,
51 but some of the regioisomeric isomers have been recently synthesized.⁷ The analysis of the
52 different metabolites is very relevant for describing the urolithin metabotypes and detecting
53 differences in the phase II metabolites produced. The differences in the occurrence of these
54 metabolites could be linked to different polymorphisms that could be related to the observed
55 differences in the urolithins' biological effects.

56 In recent years, the number of research articles devoted to investigating urolithins has increased
57 exponentially, with significant advances in the knowledge of their physiological effects⁵⁻⁷, the
58 metabolic pathways involved, and their presence in different biological samples (plasma, urine,
59 feces, and tissues).⁸⁻¹⁴ The most widely used analytical techniques rely on high or ultra-high-
60 performance liquid chromatography (HPLC or UHPLC) in reverse phase mode employing C₁₈-
61 based columns coupled to spectrophotometric (UV-Vis or DAD) and mass spectrometric (MS)
62 detectors.^{8,10,13,14} However, the separation of isomeric forms of glucuronide urolithins using
63 reversed-phase liquid chromatography has not been feasible as urolithin A 3- and 8-glucuronide

64 and isourolithin A-9-glucuronide are not resolved to enable their identification and quantification
65 eluting as a single chromatographic peak.^{7,13,15}

66 Due to the resolution limitations of reversed-phase HPLC for analyzing urolithin glucuronides,
67 other analytical methods should be explored to sufficiently separate these metabolites. A better
68 peak resolution of urolithin glucuronides is essential to evaluate the differences in metabolites
69 produced by the combined metabolism of gut microbiota, which leads to different final urolithins.
70 ¹⁶

71 One of the alternatives to HPLC could be supercritical fluid chromatography (SFC), in which the
72 mobile phase is usually composed of a mixture of a supercritical fluid and a miscible organic
73 solvent.¹⁷ The supercritical fluid, usually CO₂, has intermediate properties between a liquid and a
74 gas. Its density, viscosity, and diffusivity can be modified with changes in system temperature
75 and pressure, and its polarity can be adjusted with organic modifiers. Moreover, SFC offers
76 several advantages over HPLC, such as higher efficiencies and improved resolutions, shorter
77 analysis times, and lower consumption of organic solvents, one of the principles of green
78 analytical chemistry.¹⁸ However, it should be pointed out that, to our knowledge, no studies have
79 been published dealing with the SFC separation of the glucuronic derivatives of urolithin, neither
80 in biological samples nor in other matrices.

81 Therefore, the main goal of the present study was to investigate the potential of SFC for separating
82 five urolithin glucuronides (urolithin A 3- and 8-glucuronide, isourolithin A 3- and 9- glucuronide
83 and urolithin B 3-glucuronide), paying particular attention to separate the urolithin 3-glucuronide,
84 urolithin 8-glucuronide and isourolithin A-9-glucuronide isomers, since it has not been ultimately
85 achieved in any previous studies.

86

87 **MATERIALS AND METHODS**

88 *Reagents and standards*

89 As previously reported, the different urolithin glucuronides (see structures in Figure 1) were
90 synthesized.⁶ Standard (matrix-free) stock (\approx 500 mg/L) and working solutions of the studied
91 compounds were prepared in methanol. All the organic solvents employed (methanol, acetonitrile,
92 ethanol, isopropanol, ethyl acetate) were HPLC grade and obtained from LAB-SCAN (Dublin,
93 Ireland). Trifluoroacetic acid, formic acid, acetic acid, triethylamine, and diethylamine were of
94 analytical quality and obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (Madrid, Spain). Carbon dioxide was SFC
95 grade and obtained from Carbueros Metálicos (Barcelona, Spain). Solid-phase extraction (SPE)
96 cartridges Strata[®] C₁₈-E (3 mL; 500 mg; Phenomenex, Torrance, CA, USA), as well as a 10-port
97 Visiprep vacuum manifold (Supelco, Bellefonte, PA, USA), and Nylon syringe filters (17 mm,
98 0.45 μ m; Nalgene, Rochester, NY) were employed for sample treatment.

99

100 ***Sample procurement and treatment***

101 Urine samples were collected from ten healthy volunteers belonging to the three urolithin
102 metabotypes A, B and 0, after consuming 30 g of walnuts per day for three days. Urine samples
103 were collected on the morning of the fourth day and stored refrigerated (4 °C) until analysis.¹⁹
104 Intervention was performed following the Helsinki Declaration, and informed consent was
105 obtained from each individual. Urine samples were freeze-dried and stored at -20 °C until
106 analysed. The samples were extracted and concentrated using SPE columns as previously
107 described, with some modifications.²⁰ Briefly, each urine sample (5 mL) was loaded onto a Strata[®]
108 C₁₈-E cartridge (once conditioned with 5 mL of methanol and 5 mL of water) at about 1 mL/min
109 employing a vacuum system. The SPE cartridge was then washed with 5 mL of water: acetic acid
110 (99.5:0.5, v/v); the rinse was discarded, and after 5 min of drying time, the analytes were eluted
111 with 1 mL of methanol, which was passed through a syringe filter before the SFC-UV analysis.

112

113 ***SFC-UV conditions***

114 The SFC system was manufactured by Jasco (Tokyo, Japan). It was equipped with two pumps
115 (4380-CO₂ and 4180) for supplying the carbon dioxide and the modifier, respectively. The
116 autosampler was a 4350 model, and the injection volume was set at 15 μ L. The column was
117 thermostated in an oven (model 4065). The pressure was controlled by a pressure regulator (model
118 4380), and the detector employed was a UV (model 4095).

119 An (S, S) Whelk-O 1[®] (150 x 4.6 mm; 3,5 μ m; Regis Technologies, Morton Grove, IL, USA)
120 column was employed for SFC analysis. The mobile phase was composed of a mixture of carbon
121 dioxide and 0.1% (v/v) and trifluoroacetic acid in isopropanol (70:30; v/v) applied in isocratic
122 elution mode. The flow rate was set at 2.0 mL/min; meanwhile, injection volume, back pressure,
123 column temperature, and detection wavelength were set at 15 μ L, 130 bar, 35 °C, and 225 nm,
124 respectively. Meanwhile, the detection wavelength was set at 225 nm.

125

126 **RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

127 *Optimization of the separation conditions*

128 As mentioned in the introduction, there are no previous methods where SFC has separated
129 urolithin glucuronides, so it was decided to check the suitability of a series of chiral and achiral
130 columns with different stationary phases (**Table 1S**). Various solvents were tested as organic
131 modifiers (methanol, ethanol, isopropanol, and acetonitrile), as well as acid (trifluoroacetic,
132 formic, and acetic acids) and alkaline (triethylamine, diethylamine, and ethanolamine) additives
133 or mixtures of both. Moreover, different experiments were performed for each column by varying
134 the mobile phase's pressure, temperature, and isocratic or gradient compositions. The initial
135 conditions were the same for all columns. They were taken from previous experiments of the
136 research group: mobile phase composed of CO₂ (A) and 0.1% of diethylamine in methanol (B)
137 applied in gradient elution mode (0-7 min, from 5% B to 60% B; 7-9 min 60% B; 9-10, from 60%
138 to 5% B) at a flow rate of 2.5 mL/min, 35 °C and 100 bar. Chromatograms were registered at 225
139 nm and 305 nm and selected according to preliminary experiments (see UV-Vis spectra in
140 Supporting Information, **Figure 1S**) and the related literature.⁶ It should also be mentioned that

141 these experiments were performed without including urolithin B 3-glucuronide, as the main
142 objective was to separate those compounds which usually coelute when using HPLC. The most
143 promising results were obtained with two chiral columns, ReflectTM I-Cellulose C and (S, S)
144 Whelk-O[®] 1, both from Regis Technologies. The first column (ReflectTM) is based on a
145 polysaccharide derivative (cellulose tris- 3,5-dichlorophenylcarbamate) and is suitable for many
146 chiral compounds. At the same time, the other (Whelk-O[®]) is a Pirkle-type column with π -electron
147 acceptor/ π -electron donor interaction abilities, which offers complementary separation
148 capabilities to polysaccharide chiral stationary phases. More specifically, the Whelk-O[®] column
149 combines π -donor (tetrahydro phenanthrene) and π -acceptor (3,5-dinitrophenyl) as well as
150 hydrogen bonding sites (amide) to interact with the analytes. The preferentially bound analyte
151 interacts via face-to-face π - π interactions with the dinitrophenyl moiety and hydrogen bonds with
152 the amide function. In addition, face-to-edge π - π interactions enhance the affinity between the
153 selector and analyte.²¹ Considering the structures of the compounds studied, they could interact
154 through face-to-face π - π interactions between the dinitrophenyl ring of the selector and the
155 aromatic rings of the analytes. Hydrogen-bond interactions between the NH of the chiral selector
156 amide group and the analyte's carbonyl group could also be possible.

157 The tests carried out with the other columns were not acceptable due to several reasons: i) absence
158 of peaks; ii) poor peak symmetries; iii) non-acceptable retention times; iv) complete coelutions
159 (see some examples in Supporting Information, **Figure 2S**). Thus, the optimization procedures
160 continued with the two columns mentioned above.

161 *(S, S) Whelk-O[®] 1 column*

162 Different solvents (methanol, acetonitrile, ethanol, and isopropanol) were tested as organic
163 modifiers. Results showed that using methanol, the urolithin A 3- and 8-glucuronides coeluted
164 partially, but they were baseline separated from the isourolithin A 3- and 9- glucuronides, which
165 were overlapped, as can be deduced from the evaluation of the chromatogram and the resolution
166 values (**Figure 3S and Table 2S**). Several experiments were performed using different

167 percentages of organic modifiers, temperatures, and additives (acids: trifluoroacetic, formic and
168 acetic acids; bases: triethylamine, diethylamine, and ethanolamine), and the best performance was
169 obtained when using 0.1% of trifluoroacetic acid in methanol as an organic modifier (**Figure 4S**).
170 As can be seen, the separation between the isourolithin and urolithin isomers was better than in
171 the first tests, especially in the case of the isourolithin isomers, which resolution value was higher
172 than 2 (**Table 3S**). However, a partial coelution was also obtained between urolithin A 3-
173 glucuronide and isourolithin A 9-glucuronide. Thus, it was decided to continue the experiments
174 with ethanol and TFA as additives. The separation between the isourolithin and urolithin isomers
175 was similar to that obtained using methanol. Still, the separation between urolithin A 3-
176 glucuronide and isourolithin A 9-glucuronide improved, as can be checked by evaluating the
177 separation parameters (**Table 4S**).

178 On the contrary, the resolution between the urolithin isomers was slightly worse (**Figure 5S** and
179 **Table 4S**). In the case of isopropanol, a change in selectivity for the urolithin A glucuronides was
180 observed, but the separation was still not good enough; isopropanol does not seem to improve the
181 results obtained with ethanol (**Figure 6S**, and **Table 5S**). Meanwhile, acetonitrile was discarded
182 as most compounds were not eluted (**Figure 7S**). After testing different mobile phase
183 compositions, pressure, and temperature conditions with isopropanol, methanol, and ethanol, the
184 best results were obtained with isopropanol. By reducing the composition of the organic modifier
185 and increasing the temperature and pressure, it was possible to improve the separation of the
186 urolithin A glucuronides. It should be specified that the retention time decreased when the
187 pressure increased. This behavior could be explained by an increase in the density due to the
188 higher pressure; therefore, the solvation was more significant, which increased the strength of the
189 mobile phase.

190 Meanwhile, the opposite effect was observed when varying the temperature, as retention times
191 increased. The influence of the temperature was more complex to study because it presented two
192 opposing effects on retention. On the one hand, as the temperature increases, the density of the
193 mobile phase decreases and, therefore, the retention increases; however, increasing the

194 temperature favors the dissolution of the analytes in the mobile phase so that retention can de be
195 decreased. The observed results showed that for the four different temperatures assayed (20-35
196 °C), the retention times of the isomer pairs increased with the temperature and the resolution
197 (**Table 6S**), being the highest values obtained for 35 °C. Linear van't Hoff representations were
198 obtained for $\ln K$ and the thermodynamic parameters of the separation; meanwhile, the isoelution
199 temperatures were also calculated (see Supporting Information, **Table 7S**). I should be noted that
200 the values obtained are estimations from the linear correlations and they are not exact values. In
201 all the cases, the enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) variations were positive, which explained the
202 increase of retention with temperature. Moreover, the isoelution temperatures were below the
203 working temperature range, that means, the separation was entropically driven, and the selectivity
204 increases with the temperature. This was also experimentally observed, and the higher resolutions
205 were obtained at 35°C. In order not to damage the stationary phase and considering the
206 manufacturer's advice, higher temperatures were not assayed. In addition, better separation
207 between urolithin A 8-glucuronide and isourolithin A 9-glucuronide was also observed using a
208 lower percentage of the organic modifier. It should be noted that this possibility was also
209 evaluated with ethanol, but the separation of the urolithin A glucuronides was not improved
210 because the effect was the opposite. Thus, as can be observed in **Figure 8S**, the four compounds
211 were finally separated (resolution values higher than 1 in all cases, **Table 8S**) by using a mobile
212 phase composed of CO₂ and 0.1% of trifluoroacetic acid in isopropanol (70:30, v/v) applied in
213 isocratic mode at a flow rate of 2.0 mL/min, 35 °C and 130 bar.

214 At this point, it was added the urolithin B 3-glucuronide to the standard mixture, as this was
215 another relevant urolithin glucuronide in biological fluids that should also be analyzed and
216 resolved together with the synthesized dihydroxy-urolithin glucuronides, which was injected
217 under the selected conditions. The best possible result was obtained since this compound eluted
218 in an empty zone of the chromatogram between two of the other compounds (see **Figure 2**), which
219 was corroborated by the good resolution values (**Table 9S**), so it was not necessary to modify any
220 of the previously established conditions. Therefore, the five compounds were separated in less

221 than 15 minutes. Finally, it should be mentioned that it was decided to register the chromatograms
222 at 225 nm instead of the more conventional 305 nm as the peak intensities were higher.

223 *ReflectTM I-Cellulose C*

224 Once the optimal conditions for separating the five compounds on the (S, S) Whelk-O[®] 1 column
225 were obtained, it was decided to test the suitability of the ReflectTM I-Cellulose C column. In this
226 case, the mixture of the five compounds was used from the beginning of the optimization study.
227 The initial conditions were the optimal selected for the (S, S) Whelk-O[®] 1 column. As can be seen
228 in **Figure 9S**, the results were not acceptable. The metabolites were much more retained, and the
229 peaks were broader with poor symmetries (**Table 10S**). Then, other mixtures of 0.1%
230 trifluoroacetic acid with ethanol or methanol were tested. In both cases, the separation of the five
231 compounds was not achieved due to the coelution of some of them (**Figure 9S**). In the case of
232 methanol, four very intense peaks with suitable shapes, symmetries, and resolutions (**Table 10S**),
233 although the isourolithin A glucuronides coeluted. Meanwhile, using ethanol, the separation was
234 worse, with the central peaks corresponding to the urolithin A glucuronides being the most
235 affected, the resolutions and shapes were worse (**Table 10S**), and the coelution of the first two
236 compounds was maintained. This behavior is expected as the higher the polarity of the organic
237 modifier (methanol > ethanol > isopropanol), the greater the elution power of the mobile phase
238 so that the analytes will be less retained. This finding is related to the organic modifier interacting
239 with the analytes and the stationary phase, causing competition with the analyte for the active
240 points of the stationary phase. Thus, when the adsorption phenomena of modifier molecules occur
241 in the stationary phase, many active points of the stationary phase are blocked, and the analytes
242 would elute before the column. Thus, methanol was selected to continue with the experiments.
243 Afterward, the influence of the nature of the additive (basic or acidic) on the separation of the five
244 compounds was tested. Still, in all cases, only four signals were obtained, and the separation was
245 not as good as that obtained with trifluoroacetic acid (**Figure 10S** and **Table 11S**). It should be
246 noted that when using acidic additives, shorter retention times and better peak shapes were
247 obtained. In comparison, basic additives showed longer retention times without significant

248 changes in peak appearance and resolution (**Figure 11S** and **Table 12S**). This trend could be
249 explained by the different ionization of the analytes and the ionizable functions of the stationary
250 phase, which could provoke a change in the electrostatic interactions between the analyte and
251 stationary phase. The effect of the different chromatographic parameters (temperature, pressure,
252 and composition of the mobile phase) on the separation was also studied. The variation of the
253 temperature and the pressure does not produce changes as significant as those obtained by
254 modifying the mobile phase composition. After several tests, the best separation was obtained
255 with a mobile phase composed of CO₂ (A) and 0.1% of trifluoroacetic acid in methanol (B) applied
256 in gradient elution mode (0-5 min, 30% B; 5-10 min, from 30% B to 40% B; 10-11 min, from
257 40% B to 30% B), at a flow rate of 2.5 mL/min, 30°C and 120 bar. Under these conditions, the
258 separation of the urolithin glucuronides (A-3 and A-8) and urolithin B 3-glucuronide was
259 possible; however, isourolithin A glucuronides coeluted with each other but did not interfere with
260 the other peaks (**Figure 10S** and **Table 10S**).

261 In summary, the separation of the five urolithin glucuronides was achieved for the first time using
262 SFC and the (S, S) Whelk-O[®] 1 column, which represents a significant advance in this field of
263 research because it would be possible to determine their occurrence and concentration
264 individually. However, it should also be noted that the method developed with the Reflect[™] I-
265 Cellulose C column could be considered a valuable alternative to the selective separation of the
266 Uro-A glucuronides and Uro-B glucuronide. In addition, the elution order of the urolithin
267 glucuronides differed depending on the column.

268

269 *Analytical performance of the method*

270 To determine the selectivity of the proposed method, a set of extracts of urine samples (n = 3)
271 was injected into the chromatographic system, and the results were compared with those obtained
272 for the individual standards of the compounds under study. It was observed that the retention
273 times matched perfectly in all cases, with remarkable similarity in the UV spectra in standard and

274 urine samples (data not shown). The limits of detection (LODs) and quantification (LOQs) were
275 experimentally determined, and they were estimated to be three and ten times the signal-to-noise
276 (S/N) ratio, respectively (**Table 1**). In this regard, the noise was assessed as the distribution of the
277 response at zero analytes concentration. It should be mentioned that these values were worse than
278 those obtained with HPLC coupled to a diode array (10-20 times higher) or MS/MS (500 times
279 higher) detectors.¹³ The lack of sensitivity could be explained in this case by the fact that the
280 detector available was a Circular Dichroism model with UV detection. Still, by incorporating both
281 options, the detector is much less sensitive than a typical UV or a diode array detector. However,
282 the study's main goal was to separate the studied compounds, which was achieved, and the
283 sensitivity could be improved by using a different detector. Calibration curves (standard in
284 solvent) were constructed by plotting the signal on the *y*-axis (analyte peak area) against the
285 analyte concentration on the *x*-axis. The graphs obtained in all the calibration curves, which had
286 a wide calibration range (LOQ-150 mg/L), were straight lines, with a coefficient of the
287 determination values (R^2) higher than 0.99 in all cases, and the residual analysis revealed a
288 random scatter with no systematic trend (data not shown). Precision was expressed as relative
289 standard deviation (%RSD). The experiments were performed concurrently by repeated analysis
290 using a stock solution of the mixture of all the urolithin glucuronides (100 mg/L) and urine
291 samples ($n = 6$; intra-day precision) or over three consecutive days ($n = 6$; inter-day precision).
292 The obtained %RSD values for the areas and retention times were lower or equal to 15% in all
293 cases (data not shown).

294

295 *Application to human urine sample analysis*

296 The proposed SFC method was applied to analyze the five urolithin glucuronides in ten urine
297 samples obtained as previously described. The samples were analyzed in triplicate, and the results
298 (mean concentration values, mg/L) are summarized in **Table 1** (see chromatograms in **Figure 3**).
299 Chromatographic separation of the different isomers of urolithin glucuronides was achieved in
300 urine samples. Both isomers of urolithin A glucuronides were identified in urine samples for the

301 first time and were present in all the volunteers with similar proportions. In metabotype B
302 volunteers, the most common isomer was isourolithin A 3 glucuronide, although isourolithin A 9
303 glucuronide was also detected in some volunteers. It should be mentioned that the absence of
304 some of the studied compounds in some of the analyzed samples could be due to the low
305 sensitivity of the detector. Still, this issue should be solved using more sensitive detectors,
306 especially MS/MS, in future studies.

307 Moreover, the chromatographic separation of the different urolithin glucuronide isomers detected
308 in biological fluids (plasma and urine), namely dihydroxy-urolithin (urolithin A and isourolithin
309 A) glucuronides, is relevant as they are the primary circulating metabolites in plasma and excreted
310 in urine in humans. Their accurate determination is important for evaluating their biological
311 effects and the correct phenotyping of individuals into the urolithin metabotypes described above.
312 The urolithin aglycones present in fecal samples are resolved successfully using reversed-phase
313 HPLC analysis allows the adscription of individuals to the three metabotypes described.¹³
314 However, it is easier to get urine samples than fecal samples from volunteers in intervention trials
315 and therefore the adscription to metabotypes analyzing urine samples is essential for most studies.
316 There is an alternative of enzymatic hydrolysis of the glucuronide and sulfate conjugates present
317 in plasma or urine with glucuronidases and sulfatases to release the aglycones and then analyze the
318 aglycones. This would allow the determination of the metabotypes although relevant information
319 regarding the conjugates present in biological fluids will be missing. The available reversed-phase
320 HPLC method of choice for the analysis of urolithin metabolites in plasma and urine,¹³ does not
321 allow the desired resolution as three isomers (urolithin A 3-glucuronide, urolithin A-9-
322 glucuronide and isourolithin A 9-glucuronide)⁷ elute together in a single chromatographic peak
323 thus hampering the assignation of the metabotypes as metabolites characteristic of both
324 metabotypes co-elute. Regarding the interindividual variability observed in the biological effects
325 of polyphenols,²² the impact of the production of specific glucuronides due to different
326 glucuronosyl transferase genetic polymorphisms is also something that should be studied, as these
327 metabolites can have different effects depending on the location of the glucuronide, and therefore

328 govern the occurrence of metabolites with specific free hydroxyls that can have different chemical
329 and biochemical properties and finally potential interaction with receptors. Previous studies with
330 human cell lines *in vitro* have shown little differences in the neuroprotective effects of
331 glucuronide regioisomers of the same urolithin aglycone.²³ However, differences in other
332 biological activities cannot be discarded.

333 Finally, this study could represent an essential step in improving the urolithin metabotype
334 assignment and exploring the glucuronyl transferase polymorphisms that can also affect inter-
335 individual variations in ellagitannin metabolism and their effects on human health.

336

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343

344 **CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT**

345 The authors of this manuscript declare no conflict of interest.

346 **DATA AVAILABILITY**

347 The datasets generated during the current study are included in this published article and the
348 Supporting Information, or they are available from the corresponding author on reasonable
349 request.

350 **Supporting Information Description**

351 **Tables**

352 **Table 1S.-** Stationary phases tested for the separation of the urolithin glucuronides studied.

353 **Table 2S.-** Separation parameters calculated according to Purnell's formula referred to **Figure**

354 **3S.**

355 **Table 3S.-** Separation parameters calculated according to Purnell's formula referred to **Figure**

356 **4S.**

357 **Table 4S.-** Separation parameters calculated according to Purnell's formula referred to **Figure**

358 **5S.**

359 **Table 5S.-** Separation parameters calculated according to Purnell's formula referred to **Figure 7S.**

360 **Table 6S.-** Effect of temperature on the separation of the pairs of isomers with the (S, S) Whelk-

361 O[®] 1 column. Chromatographic conditions: mobile phase composed of CO₂ and 0.1% of

362 trifluoroacetic acid in isopropanol (65:35, v/v) applied in isocratic mode at a flow rate of 2.0

363 mL/min and 120 bar.

364 **Table 7S.-** Thermodynamic parameters and isoelution temperatures (T_{iso}) for the pairs of isomers

365 with the (S, S) Whelk-O[®] 1 column. Chromatographic conditions: mobile phase composed of CO₂

366 and 0.1% of trifluoroacetic acid in isopropanol (65:35, v/v) applied in isocratic mode at a flow rate

367 of 2.0 mL/min and 120 bar.

368 **Table 8S.-** Separation parameters calculated according to Purnell's formula referred to **Figure**

369 **8S.**

370 **Table 9S.-** Separation parameters calculated according to Purnell's formula referred to **Figure 2.**

371 **Table 10S.-** Separation parameters calculated according to Purnell's formula referred to **Figure**

372 **9S.**

373 **Table 11S.-** Separation parameters calculated according to Purnell's formula referred to **Figure**
374 **10S.**

375 **Table 12S.-** Separation parameters calculated according to Purnell's formula referred to **Figure**
376 **11S.**

377 **Figures**

378 **Figure 1S.-** UV-Vis spectra of the urolithin glucuronides.

379 **Figure 2S.-** Representative SFC-UV chromatograms obtained from a mixture of urolithin
380 glucuronide standards with different columns: **A)** Lichrosphere[®] CN; **B)** Daicel DCpak[®] PBT; **C)**
381 Spherex[™] Diol; **D)** Luna[®] HILIC.

382 **Figure 3S.-** Representative SFC-UV chromatograms obtained from a mixture of four urolithin
383 glucuronide standards (100 mg/L; 1.- urolithin A 8-glucuronide; 2.- urolithin A 3-glucuronide 3.-
384 isourolithin A 9- glucuronide; 4.- isourolithin A 3-glucuronide) using the Regis (S,S) Welk-O[®] 1
385 Kromasil column and the initial conditions (see *Optimization of the separation conditions*
386 subsection).

387 **Figure 4S.-** Representative SFC-UV chromatograms obtained from a mixture of four urolithin
388 glucuronide standards (100 mg/L; 1.- urolithin A 8-glucuronide; 2.- urolithin A 3-glucuronide 3.-
389 isourolithin A 9- glucuronide; 4.- isourolithin A 3-glucuronide) using the Regis (S,S) Welk-O[®] 1
390 Kromasil column and 0.1% (v/v) trifluoroacetic acid in methanol as organic modifier (see
391 *Optimization of the separation conditions* subsection).

392 **Figure 5S.-** Representative SFC-UV chromatograms obtained from a mixture of four urolithin
393 glucuronide standards (100 mg/L; 1.- urolithin A 8-glucuronide; 2.- urolithin A 3-glucuronide 3.-
394 isourolithin A 9- glucuronide; 4.- isourolithin A 3-glucuronide) using the Regis (S,S) Welk-O[®] 1
395 Kromasil column and 0.1% (v/v) trifluoroacetic acid in ethanol as organic modifier (see
396 *Optimization of the separation conditions* subsection).

397 **Figure 6S.-** Representative SFC-UV chromatograms obtained from a mixture of four urolithin
398 glucuronide standards (100 mg/L; 1.- urolithin A 3-glucuronide; 2.- urolithin A 8-glucuronide 3.-
399 isourolithin A 9- glucuronide; 4.- isourolithin A 3-glucuronide) using the Regis (S,S) Welk-O® 1
400 Kromasil column and 0.1% (v/v) trifluoroacetic acid in isopropanol as organic modifier (see
401 *Optimization of the separation conditions* subsection).

402 **Figure 7S.-** Representative SFC-UV chromatograms obtained from a mixture of four urolithin
403 glucuronide standards (100 mg/L; isourolithin A 9- glucuronide) using the Regis (S,S) Welk-O®
404 1 Kromasil column and 0.1% (v/v) trifluoroacetic acid in acetonitrile as organic modifier (see
405 *Optimization of the separation conditions* subsection).

406 **Figure 8S.-** Representative SFC-UV chromatograms obtained from a mixture of four urolithin
407 glucuronide standards (100 mg/L; 1.- urolithin A 3-glucuronide; 2.- urolithin A 8-glucuronide 3.-
408 isourolithin A 9- glucuronide; 4.- isourolithin A 3-glucuronide) using the Regis (S,S) Welk-O® 1
409 Kromasil column and 0.1% (v/v) trifluoroacetic acid in isopropanol as organic modifier with the
410 selected conditions (see *Optimization of the separation conditions* subsection).

411 **Figure 9S.-** Representative SFC-UV chromatograms obtained from a mixture of five urolithin
412 glucuronide standards (100 mg/L; 1.- isourolithin A 9- glucuronide; 2.- isourolithin A 3-
413 glucuronide; 3.- urolithin A 8-glucuronide; 4.- urolithin A 3-glucuronide; 5.- urolithin B 3-
414 glucuronide) using the Reflect™ I-Cellulose C column and 0.1% (v/v) trifluoroacetic acid in
415 different organic solvents: **A)** methanol; **B)** ethanol; **C)** isopropanol (see *Optimization of the*
416 *separation conditions* subsection).

417 **Figure 10S.-** Representative SFC-UV chromatograms obtained from a mixture of five urolithin
418 glucuronide standards (100 mg/L; 1.- isourolithin A 9- glucuronide; 2.- isourolithin A 3-
419 glucuronide; 3.- urolithin A 8-glucuronide; 4.- urolithin A 3-glucuronide; 5.- urolithin B 3-
420 glucuronide) using the Reflect™ I-Cellulose C column and different acid additives 0.1% (v/v; **A)**
421 no additive; **B)** formic acid; **C)** acetic acid; **D)** trifluoroacetic acid in methanol (see *Optimization*
422 *of the separation conditions* subsection).

423 **Figure 11S.-** Representative SFC-UV chromatograms obtained from a mixture of five urolithin
424 glucuronide standards (100 mg/L; 1.- isourolithin A 9- glucuronide; 2.- isourolithin A 3-
425 glucuronide; 3.- urolithin A 8-glucuronide; 4.- urolithin A 3-glucuronide; 5.- urolithin B 3-
426 glucuronide) using the ReflectTM I-Cellulose C column and different basic additives 0.1% (v/v;
427 **A)** no additive; **B)** diethylamine; **C)** trimethylamine; **D)** ethanolamine in methanol (see
428 *Optimization of the separation conditions* subsection).

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516

Graphic for Table of Contents

SFC-UV

Urine samples

Table 1.- Limits of detection (LODs; mg/L), quantification (LOQs; mg/L), and results (means of triplicate analyses; concentration (mg/L), %relative standard deviation (%RSD) lower or equal than 15% in all cases) of the investigation of human urine samples.

	urolithin A 3- glucuronide	urolithin A 8 glucuronide	isourolithin A 9- glucuronide	isourolithin A 3- glucuronide	urolithin B 3- glucuronide
LOD	6	5	7	6	7
LOQ	20	18	22	20	24
Sample1	29	32	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
Sample 2	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
Sample 3	30	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
Sample 4	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
Sample 5	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
Sample 6	<LOQ	<LOD	36	141	<LOD
Sample 7	<LOQ	<LOD	<LOQ	41	<LOQ
Sample 8	21	20	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
Sample 9	23	24	<LOD	<LOD	<LOQ
Sample 10	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD

<LOD: under limit of detection; <LOQ: under the limit of quantification.

Figure Captions

Figure 1.- Structures of the urolithin glucuronides.

Figure 2.- Representative SFC-UV chromatograms obtained from a mixture of urolithin glucuronide standards (100 mg/L). Chromatographic conditions are detailed in subsection *SFC-UV conditions*. 1.- urolithin A 3-glucuronide; 2.- urolithin A 8-glucuronide; 3.- isourolithin A 9-glucuronide; 4.- urolithin B 3-glucuronide; 5.- isourolithin A 3-glucuronide.

Figure 3.- Representative SFC-UV chromatograms obtained from volunteers belonging to different urolithin metabotypes: A) sample 8 Metabotype A; B) sample 7 Metabotype B; C) sample 10, Metabotype 0. Chromatographic conditions are detailed in subsection *SFC-UV conditions*. 1.- urolithin A 3-glucuronide; 2.- urolithin A 8-glucuronide; 3.- isourolithin A 9-glucuronide; 4.- urolithin B 3-glucuronide; 5.- isourolithin A 3-glucuronide.

Figure 1

urolithin A 3-glucuronide

urolithin A 8-glucuronide

isourolithin A 9-glucuronide

isourolithin A-3 glucuronide

urolithin B 3-glucuronide

Figure 2

Figure 3

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

SEPARATION OF ISOMERIC FORMS OF UROLITHIN GLUCURONIDES USING SUPERCRITICAL FLUID CHROMATOGRAPHY

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Table 1S.- Stationary phases tested for the separation of the urolithin glucuronides studied.

Column	Stationary phase	Technical specifications	Manufacturer
<i>Achiral stationary phases</i>			
Silica based stationary phases			
Luna [®] NH ₂	Aminopropyl bonded to silica gel	150 x 4.6 mm; 5 μm	Phenomenex (Torrance, CA, USA)
Spherex [™] Diol	Propanediol bonded to silica gel	250 x 4.6 mm; 5 μm	Phenomenex (Torrance, CA, USA)
Luna [®] Synergi Hydro	C ₁₈ polar endcapped bonded to silica	150 x 4.6 mm; 5 μm	Phenomenex (Torrance, CA, USA)
Luna [®] Omega Polar	C ₁₈ polar endcapped bonded to silica	100 x 2.1 mm; 3 μm	Phenomenex (Torrance, CA, USA)
Lichrosphere [®] CN	Cyanopropyl bonded to silica gel	150 x 4.6 mm; 5 μm	Phenomenex (Torrance, CA, USA)
Ultisil [™] XB-C ₁₈	C ₁₈	150 x 4.6 mm; 5 μm	Welch Materials Inc. (West Haven, CT, USA)
Gemini [®] C ₁₈	C ₁₈ with TMS endcapping	150 x 4.6 mm; 5 μm	Phenomenex (Torrance, CA, USA)
Kinetex [®] F5	Pentafluorophenyl with TMS endcapping	150 x 4.6 mm; 5 μm	Phenomenex (Torrance, CA, USA)
Daicel DCpak [®] PV4P	Polybutylene terephthalate coated on silica gel	250 x 4.6 mm; 5 μm	Daicel (Osaka, Japan)
Daicel DCpak [®] PBT	Poly(4-vinylpyridine) coated on silica gel	250 x 4.6 mm; 5 μm	Daicel (Osaka, Japan)
Hydrophilic based stationary phases			
Luna [®] HILIC	Dihydroxypropane, unbonded silica	50 x 2.0 mm; 3 μm	Phenomenex (Torrance, CA, USA)
Kinetex [®] HILIC	Unbonded silica	50 x 2.1 mm; 2.6 μm	Phenomenex (Torrance, CA, USA)

Table 1.- Continued.

Column	Stationary phase	Technical specifications	Manufacturer
<i>Chiral stationary phases</i>			
Polymer based stationary phases			
Lux® i-Amylose 3	Amylose tris(3-chloro-5-methylphenylcarbamate) bonded to silica gel	150 x 4.6 mm; 3 µm	Phenomenex (Torrance, CA, USA)
Regis Reflect® I-Cellulose C	Cellulose tris(3,5-dichlorophenylcarbamate) bonded to silica gel	150 x 4.6 mm; 3 µm	Regis Technologies (Morton Grove, IL, USA)
Others			
Regis (S,S) Welk-O® 1 Kromasil	1-(3,5-Dinitrobenzamido)-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrophenanthrene bonded to silica gel	150 x 4.6 mm; 3.5 µm	Regis Technologies (Morton Grove, IL, USA)
Chiralpak® Zwix (+)	Quinine -derived (8S, 9R) bonded to silica gel	150 x 3.0 mm; 3 µm	Daicel (Osaka, Japan)
Astec Chirobiotic™ T2	Macrocyclic glycopeptide antibiotic teicoplanin	250 x 2.1 mm; 5 µm	Supelco (St. Louis, MO, USA)

Table 2S.- Separation parameters calculated according to Purnell's formula referred to **Figure 3S**.

t₀ = 0.76 min		Figure 3S					
Compound	t_r / min	Rs₁₋₂ (α)	Rs₂₋₃ (α)	Rs₃₋₄ (α)	Retention factor (k)	Symmetry Factor	NTP
1	4.20	1.00			4.53	2.92	1672
2	4.68	(1.14)	0.86		5.16	2.47	1548
3	5.16		(1.12)	0.13	5.79	3.31	1370
4	5.23			(1.02)	5.88	3.23	1500

NTP: number of theoretical plates.

Table 3S.- Separation parameters calculated according to Purnell's formula referred to **Figure 4S**.

$t_0 = 0.76$ min	Figure 4S						
Compound	t_r / min	R_{s1-2} (α)	R_{s2-3} (α)	R_{s3-4} (α)	Retention factor (k)	Symmetry Factor	NTP
1	3.68	0.98			3.84	1.13	6060
2	3.86	(1.06)	0.84		4.08	1.14	7124
3	4.02		(1.05)	2.53	4.29	1.16	7074
4	4.62			(1.18)	5.08	1.13	6060

NTP: number of theoretical plates.

Table 4S.- Separation parameters calculated according to Purnell's formula referred to **Figure 5S**.

$t_0 = 0.76$ min	Figure 5S						
Compound	t_r / min	R_{s1-2} (α)	R_{s2-3} (α)	R_{s3-4} (α)	Retention factor (k)	Symmetry Factor	NTP
1	3.88	0.71			4.11	1.24	5005
2	4.03	(1.05)	1.60		4.30	1.31	5838
3	4.38		(1.11)	2.31	4.75	1.23	6416
4	4.98			(1.17)	5.55	1.28	5883

NTP: number of theoretical plates.

Table 5S.- Separation parameters calculated according to Purnell's formula referred to **Figure 6S**.

$t_0 = 0.76$ min	Figure 6S						
Compound	t_r / min	R_{s1-2} (α)	R_{s2-3} (α)	R_{s3-4} (α)	Retention factor (k)	Symmetry Factor	NTP
1	4.78	0.85			5.29	1.37	4413
2	5.07	(1.07)	0.92		5.67	1.73	3491
3	5.34		(1.06)	4.70	6.03	1.31	5259
4	7.52			(1.48)	8.89	1.79	4207

NTP: number of theoretical plates.

Table 6S.- Effect of temperature on the separation of the pairs of isomers with the (S, S) Welk-O[®] 1 column. Chromatographic conditions: mobile phase composed of CO₂ and 0.1% of trifluoroacetic acid in isopropanol (65:35, v/v) applied in isocratic mode at a flow rate of 2.0 mL/min and 120 bar.

Compounds	uro-A glucuronides			iso-uro-A glucuronides		
	Temperature (°C)	k ₁	k ₂	Rs	k ₁	k ₂
20	5.11	5.47	0.84	5.58	8.21	5.05
25	5.29	5.67	0.85	6.03	8.89	5.19
30	5.34	5.75	0.89	6.24	9.26	5.21
35	5.57	6.04	0.99	6.95	10.32	5.34

Table 7S.- Thermodynamic parameters and isoelution temperatures (T_{iso}) for the pairs of isomers with the (S, S) Whelk-O[®] 1 column. Chromatographic conditions: mobile phase composed of CO₂ and 0.1% of trifluoroacetic acid in isopropanol (65:35, v/v) applied in isocratic mode at a flow rate of 2.0 mL/min and 120 bar.

Compounds	ΔH_1 (cal/mol)	ΔH_2 (cal/mol)	ΔS_1 (cal/mol K)	ΔS_2 (cal/mol K)	T_{iso} (°C)
uro-A glucuronides	964.1	1106.2	6.5	7.2	-43
iso-uro-A glucuronides	2479.4	2597.9	11.9	13.1	-172

Table 8S.- Separation parameters calculated according to Purnell's formula referred to **Figure 8S**.

t₀ = 0.76 min		Figure 8S					
Compound	t_r / min	Rs₁₋₂ (α)	Rs₂₋₃ (α)	Rs₃₋₄ (α)	Retention factor (k)	Symmetry Factor	NTP
1	6.43	1.40			7.46	1.19	2886
2	7.15	(1.13)	1.81		8.41	1.22	3085
3	8.05		(1.13)	4.62	9.54	1.35	4691
4	10.80			(1.38)	13.21	1.45	5134

NTP: number of theoretical plates.

Table 9S.- Separation parameters calculated according to Purnell's formula referred to **Figure**

2.

$t_0 = 0.76$ min		Figure 2						
Compound	t_r / min	Rs_{1-2} (α)	Rs_{2-3} (α)	Rs_{3-4} (α)	Rs_{4-5} (α)	Retention factor (k)	Symmetry Factor	NTP
1	6.30	1.20				7.59	1.24	2505
2	7.22	(1.12)	1.57			8.50	1.20	2143
3	8.18		(1.15)	2.01		9.76	1.30	2998
4	9.37			(1.16)	2.25	11.33	1.51	3966
5	10.93				(1.18)	13.38	1.40	2998

NTP: number of theoretical plates.

Table 10S.- Separation parameters calculated according to Purnell's formula referred to **Figure 9S.**

t₀ = 0.91 min		Figure 9S-A					
Compound	t_r / min	Rs_{1,2-3} (α)	Rs₃₋₄ (α)	Rs₄₋₅ (α)	Retention factor (k)	Symmetry Factor	NTP
1	3.51	2.29 (1.38)	1.43		2.86	1.27	1045
2	4.5				3.95	1.35	1728
3	5.24		2.65 (1.33)		4.76	1.55	1639
4	6.66				6.32	1.62	2469
t₀ = 0.91 min		Figure 9S-B					
Compound	t_r / min	Rs_{1,2-3} (α)	Rs₃₋₄ (α)	Rs₄₋₅ (α)	Retention factor (k)	Symmetry Factor	NTP
1	4.13	2.13 (1.46)	0.52		3.54	1.91	1034
2	5.62				5.18	-	-
3	6.01		3.56 (1.49)		5.60	-	-
4	8.53				8.37	1.47	2318
t₀ = 0.91 min		Figure 9S-C					
Compound	t_r / min	Rs₁₋₂ (α)	Rs_{2-3,4} (α)	Rs_{3,4-5} (α)	Retention factor (k)	Symmetry Factor	NTP
1	10.58	0.92 (1.12)	0.89		10.63	-	-
2	11.73				11.89	-	1430
3	13.07		5.15 (1.49)		13.36	-	1212
4	19.08				19.97	1.33	4276

NTP: number of theoretical plates.

Table 11S.- Separation parameters calculated according to Purnell's formula referred to **Figure 10S.**

t₀ = 0.91 min		Figure 10S-A					
Compound	t_r / min	Rs_{1,2-3} (α)	Rs₃₋₄ (α)	Rs₄₋₅ (α)	Retention factor (k)	Symmetry Factor	NTP
1	6.26	0.99	0.80 (1.20)	1.87 (1.30)	5.88	-	286
2	7.60	(1.25)			7.35	-	500
3	8.96				8.85	-	441
4	11.35				11.47	-	1250
t₀ = 0.91 min		Figure 10S-B					
Compound	t_r / min	Rs_{1,2-3} (α)	Rs₃₋₄ (α)	Rs₄₋₅ (α)	Retention factor (k)	Symmetry Factor	NTP
1	7.13	0.90	0.70 (1.18)	1.23 (1.27)	6.84	-	368
2	8.65	(1.24)			8.51	-	419
3	10.08				10.08	-	385
4	12.55				12.79	5.64	690
t₀ = 0.91 min		Figure 10S-C					
Compound	t_r / min	Rs₁₋₂ (α)	Rs₂₋₃ (α)	Rs₃₋₄ (α)	Retention factor (k)	Symmetry Factor	NTP
1	9.19	2.91	0.42 (1.08)	1.14 (1.24; Rs ₄₋₅ (α) 2.74 (1.41)	9.10	-	924
2	9.93	(1.09)			9.91	-	24335
3	10.68				10.74	-	575
4	12.98				13.26	1.82	659
5	17.89				18.66	2.75	1597
t₀ = 0.91 min		Figure 10S-D					
Compound	t_r / min	Rs_{1,2-3} (α)	Rs₃₋₄ (α)	Rs₄₋₅ (α)	Retention factor (k)	Symmetry Factor	NTP
1	3.51	2.28	1.43 (1.21)	2.66 (1.33)	2.86	1.27	1045
2	4.50	(1.38)			3.95	1.35	1728
3	5.24				4.76	1.55	1639
4	6.67				6.33	1.62	2469

NTP: number of theoretical plates.

Table 12S.- Separation parameters calculated according to Purnell's formula referred to **Figure 11S.**

t₀ = 0.91 min		Figure 11S-A					
Compound	t_r / min	Rs_{1,2-3} (α)	Rs₃₋₄ (α)	Rs₄₋₅ (α)	Retention factor (k)	Symmetry Factor	NTP
1	6.26	0.99	0.80 (1.20)	1.86 (1.30)	5.88	-	286
2	7.60	(1.25)			7.35	-	500
3	8.96				8.85	-	441
4	11.35				11.47	-	1250
t₀ = 0.91 min		Figure 11S-B					
Compound	t_r / min	Rs_{1,2-3} (α)	Rs₃₋₄ (α)	Rs₄₋₅ (α)	Retention factor (k)	Symmetry Factor	NTP
1	9.41	1.31	1.63 (1.20)	3.00 (1.32)	9.34	0.86	271
2	10.88	(1.17)			10.96	2.19	1492
3	12.87				13.14	1.57	1771
4	16.64				17.29	1.71	2803
t₀ = 0.91 min		Figure 11S-C					
Compound	t_r / min	Rs_{1,2-3} (α)	Rs₃₋₄ (α)	Rs₄₋₅ (α)	Retention factor (k)	Symmetry Factor	NTP
1	14.68	1.61	2.20 (1.19)	3.76 (1.28)	15.13	2.08	911
2	17.16	(1.18)			17.86	1.44	1989
3	20.25				21.25	1.78	3310
4	25.66				27.20	1.78	5083
t₀ = 0.91 min		Figure 11S-D					
Compound	t_r / min	Rs_{1,2-3} (α)	Rs₃₋₄ (α)	Rs₄₋₅ (α)	Retention factor (k)	Symmetry Factor	NTP
1	10.58	2.61	1.14 (1.12)	3.04 (1.27)	10.63	2.07	1020
2	13.96	(1.35)			14.34	-	1852
3	15.50				16.03	-	2118
4	19.37				20.29	2.15	3701

NTP: number of theoretical plates.

Figure Captions

Figure 1S.- UV-Vis spectra of the urolithin glucuronides.

Figure 2S.- Representative SFC-UV chromatograms obtained from a mixture of urolithin glucuronide standards with different columns: **A)** Lichrosphere® CN; **B)** Daicel DCpak® PBT; **C)** Spherex™ Diol; **D)** Luna® HILIC.

Figure 3S.- Representative SFC-UV chromatograms obtained from a mixture of four urolithin glucuronide standards (100 mg/L; 1.- urolithin A 8-glucuronide; 2.- urolithin A 3-glucuronide 3.- isourolithin A 9- glucuronide; 4.- isourolithin A 3-glucuronide) using the Regis (S,S) Welk-O® 1 Kromasil column and the initial conditions (see *Optimization of the separation conditions* subsection).

Figure 4S.- Representative SFC-UV chromatograms obtained from a mixture of four urolithin glucuronide standards (100 mg/L; 1.- urolithin A 8-glucuronide; 2.- urolithin A 3-glucuronide 3.- isourolithin A 9- glucuronide; 4.- isourolithin A 3-glucuronide) using the Regis (S,S) Welk-O® 1 Kromasil column and 0.1% (v/v) trifluoroacetic acid in methanol as organic modifier (see *Optimization of the separation conditions* subsection).

Figure 5S.- Representative SFC-UV chromatograms obtained from a mixture of four urolithin glucuronide standards (100 mg/L; 1.- urolithin A 8-glucuronide; 2.- urolithin A 3-glucuronide 3.- isourolithin A 9- glucuronide; 4.- isourolithin A 3-glucuronide) using the Regis (S,S) Welk-O® 1 Kromasil column and 0.1% (v/v) trifluoroacetic acid in ethanol as organic modifier (see *Optimization of the separation conditions* subsection).

Figure 6S.- Representative SFC-UV chromatograms obtained from a mixture of four urolithin glucuronide standards (100 mg/L; 1.- urolithin A 3-glucuronide; 2.- urolithin A 8-glucuronide 3.- isourolithin A 9- glucuronide; 4.- isourolithin A 3-glucuronide) using the Regis (S,S) Welk-O® 1 Kromasil column and 0.1% (v/v) trifluoroacetic acid in isopropanol as organic modifier (see *Optimization of the separation conditions* subsection).

Figure 7S.- Representative SFC-UV chromatograms obtained from a mixture of four urolithin glucuronide standards (100 mg/L; isourolithin A 9- glucuronide) using the Regis (S,S) Welk-O[®] 1 Kromasil column and 0.1% (v/v) trifluoroacetic acid in acetonitrile as organic modifier (see *Optimization of the separation conditions* subsection).

Figure 8S.- Representative SFC-UV chromatograms obtained from a mixture of four urolithin glucuronide standards (100 mg/L; 1.- urolithin A 3-glucuronide; 2.- urolithin A 8-glucuronide 3.- isourolithin A 9- glucuronide; 4.- isourolithin A 3-glucuronide) using the Regis (S,S) Welk-O[®] 1 Kromasil column and 0.1% (v/v) trifluoroacetic acid in isopropanol as organic modifier with the selected conditions (see *Optimization of the separation conditions* subsection).

Figure 9S.- Representative SFC-UV chromatograms obtained from a mixture of five urolithin glucuronide standards (100 mg/L; 1.- isourolithin A 9- glucuronide; 2.- isourolithin A 3- glucuronide; 3.- urolithin A 8-glucuronide; 4.- urolithin A 3-glucuronide; 5.- urolithin B 3- glucuronide) using the Reflect[™] I-Cellulose C column and 0.1% (v/v) trifluoroacetic acid in different organic solvents: **A)** methanol; **B)** ethanol; **C)** isopropanol (see *Optimization of the separation conditions* subsection).

Figure 10S.- Representative SFC-UV chromatograms obtained from a mixture of five urolithin glucuronide standards (100 mg/L; 1.- isourolithin A 9- glucuronide; 2.- isourolithin A 3- glucuronide; 3.- urolithin A 8-glucuronide; 4.- urolithin A 3-glucuronide; 5.- urolithin B 3- glucuronide) using the Reflect[™] I-Cellulose C column and different acid additives 0.1% (v/v; **A)** no additive; **B)** formic acid; **C)** acetic acid; **D)** trifluoroacetic acid in methanol (see *Optimization of the separation conditions* subsection).

Figure 11S.- Representative SFC-UV chromatograms obtained from a mixture of five urolithin glucuronide standards (100 mg/L; 1.- isourolithin A 9- glucuronide; 2.- isourolithin A 3- glucuronide; 3.- urolithin A 8-glucuronide; 4.- urolithin A 3-glucuronide; 5.- urolithin B 3- glucuronide) using the Reflect[™] I-Cellulose C column and different basic additives 0.1% (v/v;

A) no additive; B) diethylamine; C) trimethylamine; D) ethanolamine) in methanol (see *Optimization of the separation conditions* subsection).

Figure 1S

Figure 2S

Figure 3S

Figure 4S

Figure 5S

Figure 6S

Figure 7S

Figure 8S

Figure 9S

Figure 10S

Figure 11S

